

Quantum Mechanics and Complex Numbers

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Quantum mechanics often deals with scalar values such as energy or spatial density at x etc. A free moving electron (say along the x direction) has fixed momentum just as in classical physics yet is represented by the complex number (wavefunction) $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$. This may also be thought of as a two vector. In this note, we attempt to argue that a two vector is needed because one tries to represent two pictures at the same time. The first is the physical fluctuation represented by $\cos(px)$ (or $\sin(px)$) present in quantum mechanics. It is physically real as can be seen by two slit interference experiments, but only manifests itself if there is an interaction which can resolve distances on the order of the wavelength $1/p$. At the same time, one wishes to link to the classical scenario of equal probability at all x for a free electron. To accomplish both, one may use a complex number or two-vector. This vector seems to map translation into rotation as will be argued, so the two occur simultaneously as in a circular polarized photon for example.

Free Electron

When discussing quantum wave functions, one often begins with a free electron wavefunction which has a momentum vector as well defined as in classical physics. If the electron does not interact (as in a two slit experiment) it appears to be classical. In fact, the wave nature of the electron was not known until the 1920s.

At the same time, it is known through experiment that the electron has “wavelike” behaviour because of the two slit experiment etc. This behaviour suggests that an electron can resolve distances of the order of its wavelength $1/p$. We argue that this is suggestive of a periodic cycle with spatial frequency of p e.g. $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$. What is the physical meaning of $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ i.e. what does it mean to have $\sin(px)$ approach 0 at 0 and 3.14 etc? We argue that it is linked to density. In the two slit interference experiment, the electron has probability to arrive at certain points and not at other in a somewhat periodic manner. Thus, spatial density is involved in its periodicity.

If that is the case, then $\sin(px)$ (or $\cos(px)$) may indicate a kind of periodic nature that imposes low probability to be at certain points (end points in the case of $\sin(px)$) within the wavelength. Thus, a probabilistic scenario arises. This becomes important in the case of a particle in a box with infinite potential walls. In classical physics, a particle simply decelerates to zero at the wall and then reflects. In a statistical picture, one only has density and so this density itself must somehow become zero at the walls. The inherent periodic wavefunction type density automatically achieves this goal. Thus, the periodic $\sin(px)$ or $\cos(px)$ density related aspect of the electron seems to be physically real as long as there is an interaction that resolves lengths on the order of the wavelength. (Note, $\sin(pave x)$ is a solution of the particle in a box with infinite potential walls, but $pave$ is the average potential. It seems that a potential in quantum mechanics does not accelerate a particle, but rather stirs up various momentum p_i states $\exp(ip_i x)$. These must interfere to ensure the density drops rapidly outside of classical turning points.)

What happens if there are no such interactions? In such a case, a free electron should behave like a classical particle. It has a momentum vector and moves with constant velocity. It has equal probability (spatial density) to be at any point x . How may one combine a $\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$ related spatial density with a constant spatial density at each point x ? We argue that one may use a two vector i.e. $\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$. The magnitude of such a quantity is 1 at each x , yet the inherent periodicity is present. $\cos(px)$ ($\sin(px)$) is periodic so one needs a compensating piece in a different dimension in order to maintain a constant. This is equivalent to viewing $\cos(px)$ as the x shadow of a line of radius 1 moving in a circle which is described by $\exp(i \text{ angle})$.

One may notice that an electron moving with positive v and one with negative v have wavefunctions of $\cos(px)+i \sin(px)$ and $\cos(px) - i \sin(px)$ respectively. Thus, for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls treated statistically (i.e. with time removed) one has a combination of the forward and negative average moving wavefunctions which combine to yield $2 \cos(px)$. (Note, matters are actually more complicated because the forward and backwards moving wavefunctions only represent an average momentum.)

Thus, using a two vector allows one to obtain the constant spatial density for a free electron at the same time as keeping the inherent $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ which is physical, but only manifests itself during interactions (which resolve distances on the order of the wavelength.)

Another way to examine this picture is to consider a periodic function in px , namely $a(px)$. This may be extended to a two vector $(a(px), b(px))$ such that a rotation of this vector is equivalent to a translation. In such a scenario, one maps a translation from classical physics into a rotation (periodic behaviour) of quantum mechanics. This same behaviour exists for a circularly polarized photon for example.

The rotation matrix is:

$$\begin{vmatrix} \cos(px) & -\sin(px) \\ \sin(px) & \cos(px) \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & -pdX \\ pdX & 1 \end{vmatrix} \quad \text{for } px=pdX \text{ with } dX \text{ very small}$$

$$\text{Then: } \begin{vmatrix} 1 & -pdX \\ pdX & 1 \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} |a(px)| \\ |b(px)| \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} |a(px) + dX p d/dy a(y)| \\ |b(px) + dX p d/dy b(y)| \end{vmatrix}$$

This leads to: $-b = da/dy$ and $a(y) = db/dy$ which has a solution of $b=\cos(px)$ and $a=\sin(px)$ A quantum particle moving to the right represents a rotation in one direction, while one moving to the left, a rotation in the opposite direction. The two-vector allows for a simultaneous classical type translation while keeping quantum periodicity.

In (1), it is noted that $\exp(ipx)$ represents circular polarization.

Interactions

As noted above, using a complex number $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ may describe both a constant density (through the modulus) for a free electron with constant p as well as containing the physically real periodicity which is spatially density related. In previous notes, we saw that $d/dx \text{ Action} = p$ where $\text{Action} = \text{Integral } dt L$, with L being the Lagrangian for a particle with

constant $v = x/t$. This holds for both the nonrelativistic and relativistic cases. One may see that a fluctuation of dX leads to a fluctuation in the classical actions of $p dX$. In taking the derivative d/dx of the Action, x and t are varied independently which is equivalent to a fluctuation, we argue. Thus, the idea of a periodic function, e.g. $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$, describing periodic positive or negative fluctuations seems to be contained in a classical object, the action.

In the above sections, we argued that the quantum (periodic) features of the electron emerge if there is an interaction that may resolve distances of the order of the wavelength $1/p$. How does such an interaction manifest itself? Given that one writes $\exp(ipx)$ to describe the electron as a two vector, one may imagine that a potential could do various things, such as:

1. Create two paths with the same momentum p as in the two slit experiment: $\exp(ipx_1) + \exp(ipx_2)$. Here x_1 is the distance from the center of one slit to a fixed point on a screen far away and x_2 , the distance from the center of the second slit to the same fixed point.
2. A phase shift may be added to $\exp(ipx)$ without p changing $\exp(ipx + \text{phase shift})$ as happens when an electron passes through a region with a magnetic potential, but no magnetic force (Bohm Aharonov effect).
3. A momentum distribution may be formed, as in bound state systems i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ becomes: Sum over p $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ where $a(p)$ is a weight.

Given the probabilistic periodic density-like nature of the electron with wavelengths of $1/p$, one may see that "interference" occurs by adding different two vectors. This is a kind of averaging procedure. In the case of a bound state (case 3), the wavefunction is real, so only $\cos(px)$ terms interfere. If one only considered bound states, one would not need the idea of a two vector, because only the quantum $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ behaviour is relevant. The two vector nature, however, is necessary for other cases and for the free electron. This is interesting as it seems that for case 2, one has a combination of the $\cos(px)/\sin(px)$ effects, but also retains the two vector components important for the free electron.

In all cases, the spatial density is obtained by taking the modulus of the wavefunction.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum mechanics uses a two vector to describe a free electron because one wishes to include two spatial density scenarios. A free electron may not interact and in such a situation, it is like a classical particle with a defined momentum. It has equal probability to be at any point x . On the other hand, if the electron interacts (two slit experiment, bound state etc), where the potential or interaction can resolve distances on the order of the wavelength $1/p$, then the inherent $\cos(px)/\sin(px)$ behaviour must emerge. One needs a model which may handle both. If one notes that d/dx Action = p then a fluctuation of dX changes the classical action by $p dX$. One may consider a periodic function such as $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ as describing such a fluctuation. For a bound state, one may take linear combinations of weighted $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ terms to find an overall average wavefunction. (The spatial density is the square of this value.) No complex numbers or two vectors are needed. One may ask, however,

how does one then describe a free electron with constant velocity with $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$. The inherent periodicity is there, but is not seen if there is no interaction which resolves distances on the order of the wavelength. One needs to obtain a constant result which becomes $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ for the interaction picture. One way to accomplish this is to use complex numbers (or two vectors) e.g. $\exp(ipx)$. This has a modulus of 1 and so describes the free electron, but interference allows for the complex part to be removed. For example, if one has a particle in a box with infinite potential walls, one may consider $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. This is a statistical picture with no time and the complex parts immediately cancel leaving $2\cos(px)$. This inherent piece, linked to statistical density, is important because it creates the zero density needed at the walls (say at $px=3.14/2$ and $px=3*3.14/2$). Furthermore, as shown in the note, the two-vector $(\cos(px), \sin(px))$ or $\exp(ipx)$ maps classical translation into rotation with the periodicity frequency of p .

In some cases, such as a particle encountering two slits or the Bohm Aharonov case, one makes use of the complex form writing $\exp(ipx_1) + \exp(ipx_2)$ with x_i being the distance from slit i to a fixed point on a distant screen and $\exp(ipx + i\text{phase})$ for the Bohm Aharonov case. This is a hybrid because it includes interactions, but also free motion.

In all cases, the modulus of the wavelength yields spatial density.

References

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